

README: Supplementary Computational Data

Title:

Unveiling the potential of lignin-derived hard carbon as anode material for Li- and post-Li-ion batteries: A computational investigation

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1. Overview

This repository contains input and output files from density functional theory (DFT) calculations and ab initio molecular dynamics (AIMD) simulations. The dataset was used to investigate the structural evolution of lignin-derived hard carbon materials and their performance as anode candidates for Li-, Na-, and K-ion batteries.

The simulations focus on:

- Temperature-driven pyrolysis (1273–1773 K)
 - Structural rearrangement and porosity evolution
 - Alkali metal insertion effects (Li, Na, K)
 - Morphology dependence on precursor architecture
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2. Computational Methods

All calculations were performed using:

- **Vienna AB Initio Simulation Package:** VASP
 - **Exchange–correlation functional:** optPBE
 - **Pseudopotentials:** PAW
 - **AIMD ensemble:** NVT (Nosé–Hoover thermostat)
 - **Simulation time:** 40 ps per trajectory
 - **Energy cutoff:** 400–600 eV
 - **k-point sampling:** Γ -centered mesh (~ 0.2 – 0.5 \AA^{-1} spacing)
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3. Folder Structure and Descriptions

3.1 lignin.beta

Description: AIMD-derived lignin model ($H_{64}C_{128}$ stoichiometry), Series beta

Purpose:

Pyrolysis simulations at 1273 K, 1573 K, and 1773 K producing. Investigation of AM insertions, AM favorability for insertion and voltage

Key data:

- POSCAR, INCAR , KPOINTS, vdw_kernel.bindat, starting the calculations
 - CONTCAR, OUTCAR, vasprun.xml: relaxed structure and total energies
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3.2 C-lignine.alpha

Description: lignin model ($H_{64}C_{128}$), Series alpha (C-lignine.alpha)

Purpose:

Pyrolysis simulations leading to lignin-C structures across 1273–1773 K

Key data:

- VASP input/output files for temperature series
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3.3 O-lignine.alpha

Description: Oxygen-containing lignin model (O-functionalized system, Series alpha (O-lignine.alpha))

Purpose:

Investigation of oxygen effects on:

- Porosity formation
- Structural stability
- Functional group evolution

Key data:

- VASP input/output files for temperature series
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3.4 MD.dif.tem.final

Description: AIMD trajectories at multiple temperatures

Purpose:

Analysis of temperature-dependent structural evolution

Key files:

- POSCAR, CONTCAR, INCAR, KPOINTS, OURCAR, vasprun.xml, vdw_kernel.bindat

Usage:

Snapshots extracted for geometry optimization and DFT calculations

3.5 lignine.gama & Ribbons

Description: lignine.gama, and nanoribbon-derived hard carbon models

Purpose:

To assess the impact of initial structural ordering and morphology dependence in generated carbon structures

Key data:

- POSCAR, CONTCAR, INCAR, KPOINTS, OURCAR, vasprun.xml, vdw_kernel.bindat
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DDEC6 charge analysis (selected systems only)

Purpose:

To quantify charge redistribution upon alkali metal insetion.

4. File Types and Analysis Tools

File	Description	Recommended Tools
POSCAR / CONTCAR	Atomic structures	VESTA, ASE
OUTCAR	Energies, forces, thermodynamics	pymatgen
vasprun.xml	Parsed simulation data	pymatgen, ASE
